

Living gentrification: Rethinking displacement in urban redevelopment processes from the perspective of Berlin-Neukölln

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1. Introduction

In sociological urban research, gentrification is described as the process of economic redevelopment of urban areas and the processes of displacement that go along with it. Thus, gentrification appears to be a process that is influenced by a variety of political, cultural, social and economic factors, yet it nevertheless appears as a relatively schematic process which occurs in a certain sequence of steps along different paths (Lees, 2000; Holm, 2009) and which appears almost inevitable for the development of inner city areas (Smith, 1979). However, the concept of gentrification has recently been challenged. Critical voices point out that it is employed rather as a combat term in the critique of neo-liberalism, and that any urban redevelopment can be defamed by calling it gentrification (Smith, 1996). On the flipside, in the 2009 summer edition of "City", Tom Slater criticized that many gentrification researchers seem to have lost their political and moral commitment to social justice and have lost sight of social inequalities (Slater, 2009), particularly when processes of urban revaluation are studied on behalf of the state and certain interest groups in a somewhat legitimatizing fashion. In his reply, Chris Hamnett, one of the researchers criticized by Slater, argues that on the one hand, class structures have changed and the share of the working class in the overall population has decreased. The increasing share of the middle class in inner city areas can thus not by default be explained by processes of displacement. Rather, other background factors must also be analysed from a scientific perspective.

In this debate about the "right" stance of research on gentrification², Slater and Hamnett mainly discuss political arguments, which appear to be too schematic. Both disregard the everyday occurrences of people's lifeworlds in the gentrified areas. In order to support either one or the other thesis, a detailed investigation within specific districts would have to be conducted.

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² This contribution does not attempt to make any statement on whether gentrification is socially desirable or problematic. We rather consider it as a problem linked to a concrete context as well as the design of this process. Hence, we use gentrification and urban revaluation synonymously.

Therefore, this contribution suggests a different approach. Rather than adding another differentiation or argument about the social nature of this driver of change in urban environments, we suggest an empirical approach from the perspective of the people undergoing these processes.

As cultural anthropologists, we are interested in how people in different social contexts organize their daily lives. In gentrification research, however, we have not found any lifeworld approaches that study people exposed to and involved in urban redevelopment processes in a comprehensive manner. Rather, the affected individuals are perceived roughly as displaced people who, to a degree, are pawns in the hands of the gentrifiers. Beyond the groups who articulate their opposition by means of demonstrations or political protests, there is a lack of knowledge about the ways of dealing with and the meanings gentrification has for the population of affected areas, including those who decide against moving out and develop other strategies such as more condensed living situations. We became aware of this missing perspective in gentrification research in connection with an exploratory ethnographic study in the Reuterkiez quarter, which is located in the Berlin district of Northern Neukölln. Our focus was on coexistence in this diverse area, and the gentrification process quickly caught our attention as an important characteristic of living together in the face of redevelopment processes under way in the neighbourhood. Much to our surprise – and against the grain of our clear empathy for those who are threatened by displacement – we found that many articulated a positive attitude towards processes of redevelopment in the quarter, even if at the same time concerns were raised about the ways in which rent increases and stronger population pressure would affect them.

Inspired by Vertovec's super-diversity approach (2007), which detects a differentiation of ethnic attributions and affiliations due to migration and residence legislation as well as an accompanying large variety of different framing conditions for the everyday life and work contexts of individual groups, we noticed more and more differentiations in how the "affected" dealt with gentrification. In the following, we therefore suggest a homologous perspective for researching the residents of areas affected by gentrification. The aim of this contribution is to initiate an empirically based and differentiated understanding for the effects of urban redevelopment processes on the people living in such areas beyond political and moral rhetoric. Alongside the different attitudes towards the urban revaluation processes among socially deprived groups in Berlin-Neukölln above-mentioned, current debates regarding the economic background of changes in urban and social processes do not take into account, or sufficient account, the different facets of symbolic displacement. In addition, urban revaluation in Berlin-Neukölln goes hand in hand with social stratification from below. Socio-economic

indicators are thus of limited explanatory power in order to address the social dynamics that go along with gentrification as a driver of social change in the district. In this spirit, it is necessary to study the effects on coexistence, and thus – also from an academic perspective – to develop starting points for a potential socially responsible management.

In this endeavour, our empirical exploration of Neukölln serves as a starting point. Our focus lies on the daily practices, the meanings, the attitudes and the coping strategies people employ in addressing the redevelopment of their neighbourhood. Meanings and practices emerge in social interaction. They are thus situated in the experience of lifeworlds and depend on the position an individual occupies within this lifeworld. In Neukölln, the majority of residents are of migrant background³ and live in underprivileged social circumstances.⁴ However, these categorisations are too broad to describe the situation of the inhabitants of Neukölln in this redevelopment process.

People live a super-diverse life and it would appear that more coordinates exist which shape their experience of gentrification. The findings of our exploratory research suggest that the expediency of mobility is formative for the practices, meanings and attitudes towards gentrification in the Reuterkiez quarter of Neukölln. With this in mind, our approach shows once again that lifeworld-oriented research is necessary to better determine the social dynamics of urban revaluation processes. The debates about the “right” stance of research in gentrification ignore the fact that also deprived groups of inhabitants endorse or even actively expedite revaluation processes to respond to urban drawbacks.

We outline our argument about living gentrification by first integrating the perspective suggested here into the current discourse on gentrification in the social sciences, and by working out the homologies, which we transfer to research on urban redevelopment processes based on the super-diversity approach. At the intersection of these two points of theoretical reference, the necessity of a differentiated perspective on the residents who are “affected” by processes of gentrification is established which takes its point of departure in the lifeworlds of the individuals undergoing it, and thus in the subjective interpretations of and the dealings with urban redevelopment processes. In a second step, we sketch our ethnographic approach to the field in Neukölln, where the data underlying this contribution was gathered and which gave rise to the occasion for the development of the approach here suggested to differentiate research on processes of gentrification regarding the interpretations and dealings undertaken

³ Share of migrants in Northern Neukölln: 52.1%, Reuterkiez quarter: 46.2%. The term ‘migrants’ refers to foreigners, Germans born abroad and children of foreigners born in Germany (Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg, 2012).

⁴ 60% of households in the Reuterkiez quarter have an income below the Berlin average. For Northern Neukölln overall, the situation is even more precarious (TOPOS Stadtforschung, 2011).

by the populations threatened by displacement. In the succeeding fourth chapter, we establish the necessity of this differentiated approach to a perspective on “those affected” by urban redevelopment processes. We suggest achieving this by looking at the data guided by the research question of which decisions and appropriateness for or against mobility by individuals become visible in the suburb in connection with gentrification. In the conclusion, we sketch future questions for research on coexistence in processes of urban redevelopment.

2. Frameworks: Living in a super-diverse, gentrifying urban area

Gentrification

In attempting to define gentrification and thus constitute a common object of research, the displacement of individuals with a low income and the simultaneous redevelopment of an urban area in its physical substance can be used as points of reference. As the forethinker of gentrification research Ruth Glass has put it,

Shabby, modest mews and cottages have been taken over, when their leases have expired, and have become elegant, expensive residences. ... Once this process of ‘gentrification’ starts in a district it goes on rapidly until all or most of the original working-class occupiers are displaced and the whole social character of the district is changed (Glass, 1964, pp. xviii-xix).

This process of displacement has been described as characterized by hegemonial relationships, meaning that the gentrifiers realize their interests against the inhabitants of an area who are endowed with comparably less resources (Redfern, 2003). As far as the interpretation of the social effects and political consequences of urban redevelopment processes in this situation of social inequality is concerned, there is a cacophony of voices in the community. As exemplified by the debate mentioned above between Slater (2009) and Hamnett (2009) about the political standpoint of the researchers, it is moral positions that are grappled with. In Slater’s words

‘Gentrification’ as a concept and political rallying cry has in many places been swept away by an alliterative garble of revitalisation, renaissance, regeneration, renewal, redevelopment, rejuvenation, restructuring, resurgence, reurbanisation and residentialisation – terms that bolster a neoliberal narrative of competitive progress (Slater, 2009, p. 294).⁵

Independent of this political debate, a tendency towards a stronger consideration of the variety and difference of urban redevelopment processes is becoming discernible. Increasingly, differentiations and contextualisations are taken into account, or at least called for, such as

⁵ In his argumentation, Slater refers to the contribution by Peck and Tickel (2002).

regarding the geographical position of a city, its specific (historically grown) characteristics and function (as a global city, metropolis, etc.) or also the transformation through general social and cultural developments (e.g. Lees, 2000; Karsten, 2003; Holm, 2009).

In our literature review on gentrification research regarding coexistence of people in urban redevelopment processes, it became apparent that this perspective has not led to a more differentiated view of populations affected by processes of gentrification. As a rule, these are rather schematically described as “displaced”. While gentrifiers and urban pioneers are often the topic of research for their redevelopment strategies, motivations for developing an area or their political and economic affiliations (e.g. Ley, 2003; Karsten, 2003), those who have to make arrangements with the new developments in their quarters rarely find attention in research. At the most, they are considered in research on processes of gentrification when those affected articulate themselves, when they initiate protests or attempt civil society participation in planning processes (e.g. Bernt & Holm, 2009). If they do not become visible in this intensity, and thus not easily accessible to gentrification research, those affected remain a collective category and are, in a manner of speaking, placed in the black box of the displaced or those threatened by displacement.⁶ While the gentrifiers are credited with spatial capital (Rérat & Lees, 2011), the gentrified are generally not perceived as capable actors. Beyond the protests, there is only incidental evidence about ways of acting and positions of those who increasingly experience the pressures of urban redevelopment and are looking for ways of coming to terms with these, for instance by densifying their own living situation by taking in relatives or subtenants in their own household (e.g. Holm 2011, p. 222). The moments of action and resistance perceivable here are certainly not to be overestimated in their effectiveness; nevertheless, they present moments of riding out, at least for a time, the hegemonial practices of the gentrifiers. Further examples can be gleaned in the individual profit from such processes, for instance when residents sell their real estate (cf. Hamnett, 2003) or the changing business models of local traders. The dealings with and adjustments to the new circumstances are a facet of social reality in processes of urban restructuring about which little can be found in current research.

Accordingly, the predominant and relatively schematic view of those living in gentrified quarters is of displaced or potentially displaced individuals. The guideline referred to by Slater (2009, p. 303f.) for research on gentrification – the “typology of displacement” by Peter Marcuse

⁶ This approach to research on gentrification, grounded in pragmatic aspects, is not without its bitter ironies. The marginalisation, which is experienced by those threatened by gentrification, is also reproduced by the researchers themselves. Even where researchers work with great political commitment for the underprivileged, they remain a category of remainders with whom dialogue cannot be established.

(1986) – is oriented exclusively at the modes and forms of displacement without focusing on the actual or potentially displaced individuals in their dealings with gentrification.⁷

Super-diversity and its implications beyond migration research

Neukölln as a suburb is characterized by migration and cultural diversity shaping and changing the face of the district for the past three centuries. Whereas the influx of international migrants (e.g. guest workers, religious refugees, refugees from war and the economic crisis 2008) and their social and economic underprivileged status have given rise to the image of a problem borough in the local and national media discourse, a new migration pattern is currently discussed in the media coverage on Berlin-Neukölln. This is the arrival of young, creative, mostly well-off and well-educated people who advance a new image of Neukölln as a hip and trendy hotspot with a vibrant urban culture. The super-diversity of residents of an area, as Steven Vertovec (2007) found using the example of London, needs to be considered as an influencing factor here. Since 2008, the district of Neukölln has been part of the EU Intercultural City Program in an attempt to transform this diversity into a positive and productive capacity. The activities of the municipality in this respect point out the importance of social and cultural heterogeneity for local development in Neukölln. With gentrification and migration, two powerful drivers of social change are present in Berlin-Neukölln. The differentiations which originate from this process were present in a variety of ways during our fieldwork, for instance when long term residents of migrant background complained about the large number of foreigners moving into the neighbourhood, referring, among others, to the Eastern European Roma people who used their newly acquired freedom to travel as part of the EU extension.

Referring to migration processes, Vertovec (2007) points to the new extent of complexity created by the influx of new migrants from the EU and Middle Eastern countries, which necessitates a further differentiation of categories of ethnicity according to a range of factors.

[T]hese factors include: country of origin (comprising a variety of possible subset traits such as ethnicity, language[s], religious tradition, regional and local identities, cultural values and practices), migration channel (often related to highly gendered flows and specific social networks), legal status (determining entitlement to rights), migrants' human capital (particularly educational background), access to employment (which may or may not be in immigrants' hands), locality (related especially to material conditions, but also the nature and extent of other immigrant and ethnic minority presence), transnationalism (emphasizing how migrants' lives are lived with significant reference to places and peoples elsewhere) and the usually chequered responses by local authorities, services providers and local residents (which often tend to function by way of assumptions based on previous experiences with migrants and ethnic minorities) (Vertovec, 2007, p. 1049).

⁷ Marcuse (1986) names four forms of displacement: Direct displacement, last resident/chain displacement, exclusionary displacement and displacement pressure.

These variables and their interaction are not entirely new, however the scale they have reached today makes them remarkable and important for social research. Vertovec distinguishes immigrants according to their legal status defined by immigration right: workers, students, spouses and family members, asylum seekers and refugees, irregular, illegal and undocumented migrants and new citizens. He suggests examining how this system of “stratified rights and conditions” (p. 1040) interacts with socio-cultural and socio-economic dimensions since most social scientists and civil servants do not know about these interchanges. There is a need for more and better research about super-diversity to foster a better understanding of its micropolitics. Moreover, he sketches the implications of super-diversity also for political processes and public policy making, such as new challenges for health care, school services and public administration due to an increasing linguistic complexity, religious variety and immigration statuses. The diversification and increasing complexity Vertovec found empirically for migrants in the UK is highly relevant for other areas of social science research including gentrification.

In our ethnographic exploration of coexistence in the Reuterkiez quarter in Northern Neukölln, it became more and more tangible that conceiving of the residents as potentially displaced individuals due to gentrification was by no means sufficient for researching the social dynamics in connection with the process of urban redevelopment in its complexity and context. Particularly, the efforts undertaken by residents for designing their area as well as the often-voiced opinion that a redevelopment of the quarter was welcome in principle cannot be adequately grasped. For research on coexistence in this super-diverse city quarter characterized by gentrification, we therefore lacked a conceptual framework with which to systematically approach the complexity in dealing with processes of gentrification as well as its effects on social interaction in the area. Similar to Vertovec’s findings for migration research, we found that other factors characterized the real-life circumstances and attitudes of people towards it and that we first had to follow those in order to gain a basis for further research on coexistence in the area. Bearing this in mind, we first analysed the data gathered in the exploratory phase in view of which factors characterized the real-life circumstances of the residents in times of gentrification, and which systematic approaches resulted from those for the analysis of coexistence in the area. As these are of an explorative nature at present, meaning they are not yet coherent but rather are put up for discussion here. They originated from the following approach in research.

3. Research approach

The interest in coexistence and everyday life in the Reuterkiez quarter of Northern Neukölln grew out of an ongoing study⁸ in a secondary school in the district, stimulating the desire to find out more about the local living circumstances. At this point, a significant amount of knowledge about the developments in the area had already been gathered from print media as well as from the researchers' own experience who, during their research, resided in Neukölln or other areas of Berlin. Under the framework of super-diversity existing in the area, we were keen to find out "how people define their differences in relationship to uneven material and spatial conditions" (Vertovec 2007: 1046), however without being primarily interested in ethnicity but rather with a research perspective oriented more generally at differences and variety.

In this endeavour, we drew on positive experiences made through collaborative research in the context of the school research project undertaken by advanced students as fieldworkers, and thus also designed the exploration of the Reuterkiez quarter as a multiperspective collaborative research process⁹ in order to arrive at a multi-faceted viewpoint. In the context of a research seminar for master students¹⁰, which focused on the development of Neukölln as a super-diverse suburb, several student researchers also participated in the collaborative exploration of the quarter.¹¹ Aside from joint data collection, the collaborative research included reflections on the research process, the discussion of relevant theories as well as processes of interpretation and analysis. This pays tribute to the increasing complexity of research areas in modern societies, which, as anthropology of the contemporary, can hardly be grasped from an individual research perspective only (Rabinow et al., 2008).

In this kind of extended research context, the researchers were able to build on existing knowledge from the school research project. Throughout the whole process, senior researcher Prof. Dr. Gertraud Koch closely supervised them. At the beginning of the research process, in the sense of a *Begehung* (Certeau, 1999)¹², a tour from the Reuterkiez quarter to the Neukölln

⁸ Three students, Christine Wagner, Mahyar Nicoubin and Anna Henke, were part of this eight-month research project and were supervised by Dr. Stefanie Everke Buchanan in weekly teleconferences. Their bachelor theses originated from this research.

⁹ The consequences, which followed for the production of insight, go beyond the framework available here and will be explored scientifically elsewhere.

¹⁰ Participants were: Maike Bechtel, Teresa Grüne, Nora Hodeige, Eva Klaus, Constanze Knupfer, Samantha Lutz, Ariane Lüsse, Sophie Minden, Jürgen Muckenschabel, Christina Pfeil, Teresa Stumpf, Alejandra Tijerina García, Sophie von Zezschwitz and Jan Zipp.

¹¹ In addition to the authors of this contribution, Sophie von Zezschwitz participated with a media analysis and Maike Bechtel and Eva Klaus contributed with participant observation and interviews during the fieldwork phase in Berlin.

¹² Christine Wagner, who lived in the Reuterkiez quarter during her own research phase at the school project and who had directly experienced the changes in the suburb during that time, guided the tour.

town hall was taken, revealing the different ways in which gentrification processes become apparent in a number of places.

During the one week field phase which followed after literature and research work within the framework of the seminar, meetings of all who were active in the field took place every night in order to share, reflect and supervise the research activities. On some occasions, two of the researchers who participated in the school project¹³ also attended this exchange. Considering this “distributed” research in a collaborative work process as well as the knowledge gathered by the school researchers on the area, the stay in the field extended over a period of around nine months. The researchers who steered this collaborative process thus were constantly present in the field in the sense of the new temporality of fieldwork as frequent stays of short duration and the constant communication with the actors via a range of media (Rabinow et al., 2008).

Along the lines of ethnographic research strategy, we thus accessed the social context of the Reuterkiez quarter in its complexity in a multi-method manner. In addition to participant observation, single and group qualitative interviews¹³ as well as quantitative data from existing socio-demographic research, we also included qualitative and quantitative content analysis from newspapers that had been conducted by students in the research seminar with different research questions. Hence, a dense web of data on different areas was spun which, in the face of the ethnographic strategies oriented at contextuality and complexity, are classified as explorative. The situational approach suggested by Vertovec as an ethnographic research strategy for research on super-diversity (following Gluckman, 1958; Mitchell, 1956; Rogers and Vertovec, 1995)

in which a set of interactions are observed and an analysis ‘works outward’ to take account of not only the meaning of interactions to participants themselves, but also the encompassing criteria and structures impacting upon the positions, perceptions and practices of these actors (Vertovec, 2007, p. 1047)

had thus begun for gentrification in Neukölln – even though it is far from being exhausted.

Not all of the data collected during our research in Neukölln are relevant for the topic discussed in this paper as they also relate to other aspects of coexistence. Nevertheless, they are mentioned as they contributed to our knowledge about the complexity of the context we

¹³ On some occasions, Anna Henke and Mahyar Nicoubin were able to participate and contribute their knowledge about Neukölln and their research experience from the school research project (Christine Wagner had moved on and lived in London for her MA). Moreover, Anna Henke, who lived in Neukölln at that time, complemented our research with her own observations on gentrification and later made her documentation on it available to us.

studied, and it was this data that gave rise to the perspective presented here. For the establishment of the typology sketched below, participant observation, five qualitative interviews (interviews 1-5), two group interviews (group interviews 1-2) and one interview as part of a guided tour (interview 6), all of them conducted with “Stadtteil-Experten” - “neighbourhood experts”, were used. By “neighbourhood experts” we refer to individuals who have been actively involved into the district’s matters of civil society over a longer period, sometimes over decades, and who particularly are in close contact with a wide spectrum of different groups of people. These interviews were evaluated in detail with the software for qualitative data analysis MAXQDA in the sense of Grounded Theory (Strauss & Corbin, 1990) in order to arrive at typologies. The coding took place as a three level process with two re-codings to clarify the types, and was constantly critically discussed with the observations made as part of the fieldwork in mind. In this process, we arrived at the following results.

4. Living gentrification

The redevelopment of Neukölln, and particularly of the Reuterkiez quarter, is visible and can be felt throughout its urban environment (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Bohemian village and renovated building in Neukölln

It is mainly driven by the public sector, e.g. being openly visible by the city’s recent participation in the “Intercultural Cities” program of the Council of Europe and the European Commission.¹⁴ The efforts undertaken to make use of the area’s “diversity advantage” are intended to dispose the image of a problem area and to help create better conditions for the integration of migrants

¹⁴ For further information see http://www.coe.int/t/dg4/cultureheritage/culture/Cities/Default_en.asp

– who constitute the majority of residents – by achieving a stronger social mixing. Another important part of this redevelopment is the construction and establishment of the school and education project Campus Rütli (see Figure 2). This redevelopment process places strong pressure towards mobility on the area's residents, both in a social as well as in a spatial sense, independently of whether they remain in the area or decide to move away. Those who stay often lose their position in the social hierarchy due to more affluent residents moving into the area, or they need to find a new position within the changed circumstances in the quarter.

Figure 2. The redevelopment of the former Rütli School to the Campus Rütli

In this sense, we approach the ways of handling gentrification in Neukölln based on the spatial decisions and opportunities about mobility made by the residents and analyse these in regard to their effects for social mobility. According to mobility researcher Vincent Kaufmann (2001, p. 38), several connections between spatial and social mobility must be considered: a) “moving and being mobile”, in which spatial and social mobility go hand in hand, b) “moving without being mobile”, in which the actors experience no change regarding their role, identity and social position, for instance business people for whom mobility is part of everyday life and c) “not moving and being mobile”, that is, changes in social position which occur without spatial mobility. The influx of “the rich” can thus be conceived of as downward mobility among those who are already on site, immediately becoming perceivable in the rising prices of apartments and businesses but also inducing symbolic distinctions.

Social mobility can potentially be thought of in two directions, upwards and downwards. We emphasize this fact since mobility is usually understood as something positive in the sense of

an upward movement.¹⁵ From the perspective of the people's geographical mobility, we therefore attempted to understand in how far their social position in the area is affected and changed by this mobility.

4.1 People who leave or are about to leave

For those residents who had lived in Neukölln for several years and then moved out, falling into the category of the displaced, our conversations with experts revealed two different motives. Following Marcuse (1986), the *physical displacement for socio-economic reasons* showed up in apartment rentals, now rented out to students who pay by room but formerly inhabited by larger families of Turkish or Arab descent who now have had difficulties finding affordable housing (group interview 1). A second, albeit different facet of displacement, refers to those leaving the area because it undergoes *too little* redevelopment. They decide to move out of the "problem borough" Neukölln because they expect better living conditions for their families in other places. An important motive for leaving an area is linked to children education opportunities. Among other motives, third generation migrants who had completed a university education and acquired better income opportunities were considered here. These individuals move to areas such as Bukow and Rudow because they hope for a more advantageous school context (interview 1, 2012).

This moving away by groups who are better off in terms of education and income¹⁶ contributes to apartments becoming vacant, and thus potentially available for renovation. Furthermore, it shows that upward social mobility, as a dynamic force, is apparently difficult to achieve from the inside and for the current resident population.

¹⁵ This, too, should be seen as an extension of perspective in gentrification research, which considers processes of revaluation in suburbs but conducts little research on the social dynamics connected with them.

¹⁶ Some initial attempts of an opposite movement could be discerned in Neukölln: parents deciding to stay in the area and actively involving themselves in local school politics. One example of this is the initiative "Kiezschnule für alle" (local school for all), in which mainly German parents are organized and actively become involved in the design and organisation of the primary schools.

However, displacement often does not occur physically but via subtle symbolic mechanisms due to the district's new atmosphere and spatial concept of shifting sceneries and facilities, excluding people from participating in public life¹⁷ (Marcuse, 1986). In this sense, a new atmosphere in the urban area of the Reuterkiez quarter could be found, albeit not as distinct symbolic compositions¹⁸ but rather ambivalent and not revealing at first glance in how far they have had an inclusive or exclusive effect. Such a case can be found in the structure and the appearance of the district's BiOriental market (see Figure 3). In registering an outflow of Turkish-Arab clientele, the market experienced a loss of customers.¹⁹ In 2007, a major reorganisation process of the market's structure was initiated, indicated in the renaming of the market from Türkenmarkt to BiOriental market.

Figure 3. Field notes – Map of the restructuring process of the market

¹⁷ This change of atmosphere manifested itself much more clearly in the school research project: the slow increase in pupils of German descent gave rise to the question of how the participation of migrant mothers in the parent coffee sessions that had finally been achieved could be maintained and protected from displacement by “Latte Macchiato Mothers” (a colloquial term used to refer to mothers who focus mainly on the education and care of their children from the highly educated middle class).

¹⁸ The Comenius garden, for instance, which is open to everyone as long as the requirements of silence and contemplation are met, makes other positings in the sense of inclusion and exclusion, which are beyond social and economic categories. Here, in everyday life it is often the newly arrived students with their specific leisure time demands to whom the use of this space is denied (group interview 1, 2012).

¹⁹ This gives rise to the question – to be addressed separately – about the causes of this decrease and whether it can be traced back to a change in consumption patterns, as with social statistics this displacement cannot be explained.

The market manager's aim to increase diversity and to attract traders with an organic product range at the same time threatens traditional vendors to lose their market stand and source of income (interview 2, 2012). In many cases, the market's new focus is not simply explained along ethnic categories, it rather faces and fosters new consumption demands in the sense of a "lifestyle-oriented" product range. Furthermore, the "closing of ranks" can potentially be understood as symbolic displacement (see Figure 4). Nevertheless, the new concept has also stimulated occasions for meetings between the different groups, which could occasionally be observed.²⁰

Figure 4. The quark bar & coffee market stands are some of the new lifestyle products at the BiOriental market

Moments of symbolic displacement are, however, evident with regard to the direct living environment when particularly students as neighbours of migrant families are perceived as disconcerting and threatening. The lifestyle with different daily rhythms, many visitors and the frequent tenant changes in shared student apartments are inconsistent with the habits of predominantly migrant families and their former, often longterm neighbourhood relationships (group interview 2, 2012).

²⁰ A female customer at the BiOriental market, for instance, reported that she joined up with other customers at the market and shared the vegetables sold by the crate by the Turkish traders among each other.

The mobility pressure due to symbolic displacement in the area thus proves to be a dominant factor. Simultaneously, it points to the fact that this symbolic area is a central starting point if redevelopment in Neukölln is to be successful with regard to social mixing and integration. The necessity for managing these processes becomes tangible (interview 3, 2012) in order to prevent developments at the symbolic level, which make physical displacement much easier.

4.2 People who stay in Neukölln

Among the group of those who stay, different ways of handling the urban redevelopment processes can be found, suggesting that further research into the differentiations within this group is necessary.²¹ Here, we can only provide a first rough version as it would require more detailed research. A large share of this population *remains passive* and therefore has almost no presence in public perception. On the other side, there are those who *actively engage* in the configuration of their neighbourhood by taking part in initiatives, clubs, projects and institutions, both on a voluntary and a full-time basis. From this group, most of the partners for our expert interviews were recruited. Furthermore, we assume the existence of a third party being hard to reach in our research context as they act in *illegal contexts* and use illegal means to defend “their” territory. We only came into touch with them indirectly, for instance when we heard shootings at night or when one of our interview partners made suggestions towards cases of money laundering.

An important factor of attachment to Neukölln for those who stay is the familiarity with the place and the neighbourly exchange with people in their direct surroundings (interview 1, 2012). Beyond this, it is often the lack of alternatives rather than a voluntary decision, which allows individuals to remain in their social and spatial circumstances. There is a lack of cultural, social and economic capital in order to actively design their real-life circumstance, for instance by becoming active in their social environment (interview 5, 2012). Even if there is an interest in such activities, the relevant individuals and families are unable to participate because they cannot find access. A neighbourhood that is reliable and at least similar in their living situation presents an important safety factor when there is little or no capacity for personal range of action. This is not renounced voluntarily, and it becomes threatening for one’s identity if it

²¹ The TOPOS study on Neukölln (2011) offers data on residence length in the area as follows: 12 years in Northern Neukölln overall and 12.3 years at the Reuterplatz. Migrant households have a different length of residence, (Reuterplatz: migrants 9.3 years and Germans 13.7 years). The term ‘migrant household’ refers to households having at least one foreign member or households having at least one member that obtained the German citizenship or households with members communicating in languages other than German.

disappears because of changes from the outside. Staying in Neukölln is thus often a stopgap solution because the changeover into a better living environment does not succeed or the preconditions for it are simply lacking. Independent of whether these people decide for or against moving, they will most likely be unable to improve their social situation.

On the other hand, individuals who command enough capital to become active often show interest in creating a positive development in Neukölln through their personal involvement. This group could just as well decide to leave Neukölln without giving up or worsening their own social position. However, it is precisely them who can contribute in a significant manner to a positive development of the area, and it is emphasized time and again how important their remaining in the area is (interview 3, 2012; interview 4, 2012). The change in population, which thus occurs from the inside due to the change of the social position of the current residents, is therefore seen as central for a positive development of an area. When this group increasingly decides against moving out, this is one step and one indicator for the development of a sustainable suburb design. These activities by committed individuals in the area are thus on the one hand part of the symbolic redevelopment and can be critically viewed as a symbolic form of displacement, as done by Marcuse (1986). Frequently, it is the newly arrived artists or students who approach people and together with them actively contribute to the redevelopment, which often earns them the attribute “gate opener” for gentrification (interview 5, 2012; Giffey, 2013). This shows the dilemma in which those who want to become active in improving the living situation in the area find themselves in, and who can be classified into a wide spectrum of different actors according to their personal and institutional backgrounds, motives, means, starting points and capacities. These people do not simply feel bound to their work but also with the community of Neukölln. The motives of their personal commitment are diverse. On the one hand, personal engagement addresses the inside of the district, i.e. social cohesion among the people spending their daily life in the district itself, but also artistic activities, the design of public space, activities relating to image and many more.²²

²² For instance: In celebrating the diversity of the district, this year’s festival 48 STUNDEN NEUKÖLLN (48 hours Neukölln) main theme “EndstationParadies” (final destination: paradise) countered Neukölln’s negative image of “Endstation Neukölln”, which continues to be ascribed from the outside.

Figure 5. The entrance gate of the Comenius Garden

Working, however, is mostly not only perceived as a financial reimbursement but also as an honorary capacity as the example of the Comenius Garden outlines (interview 6, 2012; see Figure 5). It shows that individuals engaging in the development of Neukölln offer potential for identification with the district itself for locals and Neukölln's youth. They follow diverse motives of getting actively involved in shaping the future of the district. It is their sense of responsibility towards the community, their identification with local role models ("Originale aus dem Volk", Trommer, 2006, p. 33) and their identification with self-induced projects rather than originating from an external cause. Such self-initiated actions and projects do not only strengthen one's personal identification with the district, but also those of others regardless of whether they are "residents for life" or "residents only for a time" (Trommer, 2006, p. 35). They develop very different ideas about what Neukölln should look like and which paths could be taken to achieve a socially inclusive Neukölln. They all have in common that they are democratic and socially inclusive activities, which act on these principles. Arguments, friction and conflicts are included

because different ideas about the urban space and its potential are negotiated, as exemplified by the conflicts surrounding the garden plot colony on the future Campus Rütli (see Figure 6).²³

Figure 6. Signs at the garden plot that says “Freedom for the gardens” and at an empty shop window in the Reuterkiez quarter as forms of protest

4.3 People who come and go

This category refers to people visiting, people working and people living in the district only *temporarily*. Each of these dimensions considers the level of time intensity spent in the district by the individuals. The social positioning of these individuals is not affected by staying or moving out of Neukölln. Rather, mobility is part of the social identity of this group, and Neukölln is one of many places at which they can fulfil themselves. Their spatial commitment tends to be low, even if a temporary involvement in the area takes place. Nevertheless, their influence on the development of the area becomes apparent in shops (products for tourists), cafés (providing wireless internet; hipsters) and project-oriented locations (co-working space, party locations as transitory uses, art projects, etc.) (see Figure 7).

²³ Another example for such a conflict is the BiOriental market mentioned above. In order to defend its place, the market area will be limited at the expense of the vendors not contributing to an “interesting” and exotic range of products – and consequently being threatened by symbolic and physical displacement (interview 2, 2012).

Figure 7. Shop window sign that says “Delicatessen store soon to be opened” and advertisement for a co-working space that says “Working where other people spend their holidays”.

The first dimension, individuals visiting Neukölln, refers to those that come into the district as leisure seekers. These individuals visit for short periods and are interested in getting to know the district’s character without formally living or working there. This group is partly comprised of tourists who want to get to know the district as it has risen in popularity and who bring money to the local economy. This can be observed in the rise of recommendations of the BiOriental market – former Türkenmarkt – in Berlin tourist and traveling guides (interview 2, 2012) as an important tourist attraction.

Other individuals considered as part of the visiting dimension are students and artists who carry out their leisure activities in the district and are just passing by. This group has increased since the opening of the Tempelhofer Feld, which attracts people to carry out leisure activities, though the percentage of students and artists has always been significant due to low rents (interview 5, 2012). These individuals are characterized by the drive of getting to know a new place and enjoying its qualities based on spending short periods of time. Their involvement is only linked to leisure activities (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. "Musikinsel" at the lower end of the BiOriental market

Other people come for working in the district but live elsewhere in or outside of Berlin, like the day-traders who come to the BiOriental market to sell their products and then leave after the market is closed (interview 2, 2012), or artists who look for special spatial qualities for their projects and come only temporarily. Even if they come to live here for a limited or specific period of time, such as students do, Neukölln is not linked to their social identity and to some extent interchangeable for what these people consider as their main activities (interview 5, 2012). The district's newfound popularity amongst groups of artists and students is visible through the rising numbers of these groups in the district and the impact they have in its atmosphere (interview 6, 2012). On the basis of this, the district welcomes and ascribes positive meaning to redevelopment processes caused by the spatial mobility pattern of people who come and go to Neukölln. However, it remains unclear in how far this temporary attractiveness for certain groups is positive or hindering for the development of the area (interview 4, 2012). All the individuals in the three mobility dimensions previously mentioned (visiting, working, living) share one thing in common: Neukölln as a place of temporary exchanges. The exchanges vary in intensity depending on the mobility dimension these individuals fit into. The combination of these mobility patterns reshapes the atmosphere and composition in how people experience the urban restructuring processes.

4.4. People who come to stay in Neukölln

Finally, we would like to focus on the group of those who move to Neukölln in order to *stay for longer*. According to the cliché of gentrification, this includes young families who regard the revaluated neighbourhoods as a convenient living environment to raise their children. Although this group of people has just started to discover the district as being suitable for their needs, there seems to be a rising trend. The middle class mothers mainly caring for the well-being of their children have become the most visible tokens for this development in urban areas. Ironically and metaphorically they are called “Latte Macchiato Mothers”. In contrast to the hipster groups, tourists and other well-to-do flaneurs (Bauman, 1994) who conceive of Neukölln only as a point of transit, it is also the educated members of the middle class who improve their social standing, at least from the point of view of living, by moving into the area and who have significantly characterized both the term and the phenomenon of gentrifier. This is only partly true for Neukölln because aside from the flaneurs and the gentrifiers, who each can be attributed with a share in the current redevelopment process, there is also a large population of people in precarious living situations. This population can be identified as those who migrate to Neukölln as part of the economic crisis in Europe, or those who take advantage of the free movement that came along with the eastward extension of the European Union, in their hope for a better living and earning chances in the quarter. Like in the other categories, this includes a very diverse group of people from various backgrounds following different motives. In Neukölln, it includes the inflow of Roma families who emigrate from their home countries into the district to start a new life. Since the accession of Bulgaria and Romania to the European Union, especially since the year 2009/2010, big clans of Roma move to Germany and increasingly to Berlin-Neukölln. They often live in precarious conditions, crowded in small apartments (interview 1, 2012). The Roma families, although a very diverse group in themselves, mostly live off small trade earnings, occasional jobs, begging and at times from illegal transactions. Combined with state and child support, this allowance rises above the income they earn in their home countries (Roma-Statusbericht, 2012). With this in mind, the inflow of Sinti and Romanies symbolizes a confinement to lower social classes already living in Neukölln affecting their mobility patterns, and finally resulting in displacement competition (interview 2, 2012). The mobility pressure in Neukölln is thus of a dual kind, which makes it particularly intense for the resident population. Rental prices are rising not only because of renovations but also in the lower segment for apartments in bad conditions as these can be rented by bed or by room to Roma families who are used to precarious living conditions. At the same time, these put pressure on the labour market in the low wage segment and cause increased competition here as well.

5. Discussion

The ethnographic exploratory research showed that the options for action and handling strategies are significantly linked to individual mobility patterns respective to mobility expediencies of individuals and groups, keeping in mind that these must be thought of as a complex construct. Mobility includes both spatial as well as social dimensions; only where the two combine does more than mere “movement” (such as shopping) occur in space. Social mobility is oriented upwards and downwards. The expediency for movement in the way in which it can become necessary because of the pressure caused by processes of gentrification is fundamentally linked to the social, cultural and economic capital that is available to individuals for designing their position in social space in respectively different social spaces. Therefore, processes of gentrification hold a variety of different understandings for the residents of an area depending on their social position and their capacity for responding to the mobility pressures and promises that always go along with urban redevelopment processes. While migrants at the lower end of the social scale see themselves threatened in their physical and social existence, residents who are better capital-equipped can gain options for social mobility, perceive the redevelopment process as a positive development and be able to support and manage it accordingly.

For further research on the effects of gentrification on an area’s social cohesion and its different populations, it is necessary to gain a better understanding of the residents’ mobility expediencies. The ability to relate to the given social and spatial conditions and to move among them is different from person to person. The mobility researcher Vincent Kaufmann (2011) has coined this aptitude under the term *motility*, described as a complex concept:

Individuals and groups are characterized by their aptitude for movement within a given physical, economic and social context. The ensemble of these aptitudes may be described as motility. Motility is comprised of those factors that define an individual’s capacity for movement, or being mobile (e.g. physical capacity, revenue, training, aspiration for a sedentary or mobile lifestyle, transportation and telecommunications systems and their accessibility, skills like driving or English for travel) as well as the conditions of access that make utilizing these offers (in the broad sense of the term) possible, aptitude (the skills required to utilize the offer) and enactment (using the offer to realize projects). Motility then is the way an individual or group takes possession and utilizes the field of possibilities with regard to movement relative to his personal aspirations and projects (Kaufmann, 2011, p. 37).

In the further course of research, it therefore needs to be asked in how far this concept can be made fruitful for a more precise outlining of individual mobility expediencies in the case of individuals and groups in an area and to ask in how far these typologies for those affected by processes of gentrification can yield results. This is particularly useful and necessary when the

aims of inclusion and integration are to be achieved, which, from the point of view of the political and administrative actors, often present the central motive for initiating processes of urban redevelopment.

6. Conclusion

Starting from the debate about the social effects of gentrification on the residents of a revalued area, this contribution suggests studying the lifeworld connections of gentrification processes. For the work on this research design, we suggest a differentiated view of the population affected by gentrification in a homologous perspective to Vertovec's concept of super-diversity, which fans out ethnic categorisations in view of a differentiation due to criteria of immigration and residency. Based on the explorative research in the Berlin suburb of Neukölln, we believe the mobility patterns and expediencies of individuals and groups to be a significant factor for these differentiations. The consideration of four mobility patterns – emigration, staying, coming and going as well as immigration – in connection with gentrification in Neukölln has shown that these are linked to very different mobility expediencies, and that particularly the upwards or downwards movements in social positioning are highly significant. They influence how the redevelopment processes and the mobility pressures which go along with it are perceived and which spectrum of possibilities for reacting to them are available respectively are used. For further research on the lifeworld consequences of gentrification and coexistence in such situation, we suggest to closely examine the mobility expediencies of the residents and to assess in how far these can be typologised using the concept of motility.

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